

Humic acid, EDDS and EDTA induced phytoremediation of cadmium contaminated alluvial soil by *Calendula officinalis* L.

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Abstract : The potential of *Calendula officinalis* L. for chelate induced phytoremediation of cadmium (Cd) contaminated alluvial soil (pH 7.8) was investigated under pot experiment. Applied Cd at 30 mg kg⁻¹ and EDTA at 5 mmol kg⁻¹ caused significant reduction in plant dry biomass (29.73% and 26.69% for root and shoot, respectively). The combinatorial treatment T₁₇ [Cd 30 mg kg⁻¹ + 2 g kg⁻¹ humic acid (HA) + 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDTA] caused maximum Cd-accumulation in root, shoot and flower up to the extent of 115.96, 56.65 and 13.85 mg kg⁻¹, respectively, while the results were observed at par under the combinatorial treatment T₁₈ [Cd 30 mg kg⁻¹ + 2 g kg⁻¹ HA + 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDDS], up to the extent of 108.42, 55.85 and 13.72 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. The combinatorial treatment T₁₂ [15 mg kg⁻¹ Cd + 2 g kg⁻¹ HA and 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDDS] showed maximum remediation ratio (RR = 0.69%) among all eighteen treatments. Applied Cd (≥ 15 mg kg⁻¹) altered the chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene contents of the plants while application of humic acid enhanced their contents by 4.2–7.35%, 8.24–13.64% and 7.04–8%, respectively, over non-humic acid treated pots. The study reveals that application of EDDS is more eco-friendly than that of EDTA either individually or in combinations. The authors conclude that *Calendula officinalis* L. has potential to be safely grown in moderately Cd-contaminated soils; and application of humic acid and EDDS boosts the photosynthetic pigments of the plants, leading to enhanced clean-up of the cadmium-contaminated soil.

Keywords : *Calendula officinalis* L., cadmium, photosynthetic pigments, humic acid, EDTA, EDDS, remediation ratio.

Introduction

Heavy metals make a significant contribution to environmental pollution as a result of anthropogenic activities such as mining, smelting, electroplating, energy and fuel production, power transmission, intensive agriculture, sludge dumping, military operations and un-hygienic approach of rapidly growing population such as application of heavy metal containing fertilizers (i.e. superphosphate) or pesticides in agricultural soil¹⁻³. They present a risk for primary and secondary consumers and ultimately to humans. Due to high Cd²⁺ mobility in the soil-plant system it can easily enter into food chain and create risk for humans, animals, plants and the whole environment⁴.

Contaminated soil can be remediated by physical, chemical or biological techniques but the physical or chemical methods can be very costly and also destructive to the soil. Phytoextraction, one of the biological techniques, has been proposed as an eco-friendly *in situ* remediation

technology for contaminated soils^{5,6}. However, due to limited efficiency of metal hyper accumulator plants, chelate assisted phytoextraction has been proposed^{7,1}. The chelating amino polycarboxylic acid and ethylene diamine tetraacetate (EDTA) has been proven to enhance plant accumulation of heavy metals^{8,9}, however, the use of EDTA in phytoextraction has not been found to be suitable^{7,10}. Also the amount of metal taken up by plants has been reported to be much less than the amount mobilized from the soil during EDTA induced metal phytoextraction¹¹. Ethylene diamine disuccinate (EDDS), an easily biodegradable chelant, has been proposed as an alternative eco-friendly phytoextraction assister to be used for enhanced phytoextraction purposes. It forms strong complexes with transition metals and radionuclides to cause much smaller leaching of metal down the soil profile than EDTA¹²⁻¹⁴.

The bioavailability and mobility of heavy metals use

mainly two approaches : lowering soil pH and adding synthetic chelates¹⁵; however, these methods have some limitations due to negative effects on the chemical, physical and biological properties of the soil and groundwater. To avoid some of these constraints, the use of humic substances for increasing the solubility of metal cations and their bioavailability to plants, are being practiced¹⁶. Humic acid (HA) provides organic macromolecules with an important role in the transport, bioavailability, and solubility of heavy metals¹⁷.

With this perspective regarding problems associated with cadmium toxicity and its possible solution through selection of eco-friendly chelates for their possible combination to induce phytoextraction, the present study was implemented with an aim to explore the possibility of phytoremediation of the Cd-contaminated soils through growing a non-field crop (ornamental plant), *Calendula officinalis* L. The objectives of this study were (1) to compare the biomass production and cadmium bioaccumulation, at different concentrations of Cd addition with or without application of EDTA, EDDS and humic acid and (2) to investigate the potential of *Calen-*

dula officinalis L. for enhanced cadmium-phytoremediation through application of EDTA, EDDS and humic acid.

Results and discussion

Effect of cadmium and chelation on dry biomass :

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that humic acid (T₄) individually produced maximum root and shoot dry biomass up to the extent of 1.58 and 6.46 g pot⁻¹, respectively. Application of humic acid under Cd treated pots at 15 and 30 mg/kg increased root dry biomass by 8.82% and 21.62% and shoot dry biomass by 2.87% and 7.17%, respectively as compared to untreated HA pots, which clearly showed ameliorative role of humic acid on the biomass yield^{18,19}.

The combined application of 2 g kg⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDDS + 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd decreased the dry biomass of root and shoot by 9.09% and 18.87%, respectively, as compared to the control. The combined application of 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDTA and 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd caused maximum reduction in dry biomass of root and shoot of plants to the extent of 29.73 and 26.69% respectively, as compared to control. However, the combined application

Table 1. Effect of cadmium and chelation on dry biomass of *Calendula officinalis* L.

Treatment	Dry biomass (g pot ⁻¹)	
	Root	Shoot
T ₁ = Control	1.44 ± 0.10	6.36 ± 0.12
T ₂ = Cd 0 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.42 ± 0.05	6.34 ± 0.08
T ₃ = Cd 0 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.46 ± 0.08	6.37 ± 0.04
T ₄ = Cd 0 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid	1.58 ± 0.06	6.46 ± 0.09
T ₅ = Cd 0 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.45 ± 0.10	6.38 ± 0.11
T ₆ = Cd 0 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.52 ± 0.11	6.44 ± 0.10
T ₇ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹	1.40 ± 0.10	6.32 ± 0.12
T ₈ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.36 ± 0.18	6.28 ± 0.16
T ₉ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.41 ± 0.06	6.30 ± 0.08
T ₁₀ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid	1.48 ± 0.07	6.46 ± 0.10
T ₁₁ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.43 ± 0.11	6.31 ± 0.06
T ₁₂ = Cd 15 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.45 ± 0.05	6.52 ± 0.07
T ₁₃ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹	1.22 ± 0.06	5.14 ± 0.05
T ₁₄ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.11 ± 0.08	5.02 ± 0.09
T ₁₅ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.18 ± 0.03	5.11 ± 0.08
T ₁₆ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid	1.35 ± 0.04	5.38 ± 0.11
T ₁₇ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDTA	1.23 ± 0.05	5.21 ± 0.04
T ₁₈ = Cd 30 mg kg ⁻¹ + 2 g kg ⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg ⁻¹ EDDS	1.32 ± 0.02	5.35 ± 0.09

Note : ± values indicate standard error having three replications; EDTA = ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid; EDDS = ethylene diamine disuccinate.

of 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDDS and 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd caused 22.03 and 24.46% decline in dry biomass of root and shoot respectively over the control²⁰.

Visual symptoms of toxicity such as chlorosis and necrosis on leaves of *Calendula officinalis* L. were observed after 15 days of treatments with EDTA and EDDS. *Calendula officinalis* L. indicated a greater phytotoxic effect of EDTA than EDDS addition^{21,22}. Reduction in plant growth after EDTA treatment is probably due to the toxicity of EDTA itself and EDTA metal complexes²³. It is likely that longer exposure to chelates may reduce the biomass of *Calendula officinalis* L. However, it is also expected that the longer the plants stay absorbing metals, the higher will be the amount of metal extracted. Thus, high biomass production by plants treated with less phytotoxic chelates could be a key factor for removal of cadmium from soil.

Effect of cadmium and chelation on bioaccumulation of cadmium :

The data graphically presented in Fig. 1 indicated that cadmium addition (0 to 30 mg kg⁻¹) significantly ($P < 0.0001$) enhanced the concentration of Cd in the root, shoot and flower of *Calendula officinalis* L., which were observed from 3.58 to 42.21 mg kg⁻¹, 1.25 to 18.79 mg kg⁻¹ and 0.75 to 9.98 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. The individual effect of cadmium, chelates and the interaction between Cd and chelates were observed highly signifi-

cant. *F*-values for Cd-bioaccumulation in root, shoot and flower was observed 28.39 mg kg⁻¹ ($P < 0.0001$). Roots showed higher contamination with cadmium as compared to shoots and flowers. The combined treatment of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd + 2 mg kg⁻¹ humic acid + 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDTA per pot registered the highest bioaccumulation of Cd (115.96, 56.65 and 13.85 mg kg⁻¹ in root, shoot and flower, respectively) in *Calendula officinalis* L. For the chelates tested, the order of the effectiveness in increasing Cd desorption from the soil was EDTA > EDDS > HA. The study clearly indicated that EDTA enhanced Cd translocation from soil to root/shoot/flower as compared control pots^{24,25}. The chelating EDTA enhanced the shoot accumulation of heavy metals, but its use in phytoextraction might not be suitable due to its high environmental persistence, high solubility in soil, rapid metal mobilization, low-biodegradable property, which lead to secondary contamination resulting in an elevated risk of adverse environmental effects as reported earlier^{7,10}.

The combined treatment of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd and 5.0 mmol kg⁻¹ of EDTA increased the concentration of Cd in root, shoot and flower up to 85.46, 40.32 and 12.65 mg kg⁻¹. However, the results were observed at par under the combined treatment of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd and 5.0 mmol kg⁻¹ of EDDS to the extent of 75.86, 38.38 and 12.46 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. The present study suggests to use EDDS, a biodegradable chelator, preferably for enhanced phytoextraction of Cd from soil as leaching of cadmium complexes through the soil profile could be efficiently prevented by using EDDS instead of EDTA as reported earlier^{9,12,26,27}.

The study demonstrates lasting effectiveness of various synthetic chelates in mobilizing metals from soils to plants. However, there is concern for high metal leaching as well in spite of the increased uptake of metals by roots^{11,23}. The study also reveals that dosage of chelates should be minimized from the present level of 5.0 mmol kg⁻¹, in order to minimize the risk of plant toxicity as well as leaching from soil²⁸. However, traditional organic materials have been found more effective and environmentally friendly amendments than EDDS in enhancing phytoextraction efficiency of Cd-contaminated soil¹.

The application of 2 g kg⁻¹ humic acid per pot individually increased the Cd bioaccumulation by 23.46%,

Fig. 1. Bioaccumulation of cadmium in root, shoot and flower of *Calendula officinalis* L.

48% and 20% through root, shoot and flower of *Calendula officinalis* L., respectively. The combined treatment of Cd 30 mg kg⁻¹ and 2 mg kg⁻¹ humic acid per pot registered higher bioaccumulation of Cd (56.74, 35.77 and 12.42 mg kg⁻¹ in root, shoot and flower, respectively) in *Calendula officinalis* L.¹⁸ which indicated that humic acid could promote the transformation of cadmium from easily bioavailable fractions to potential bioavailable fractions^{44,45}. Application of humic acid for enhanced Cd-hyperaccumulation through *Calendula officinalis* L. has also been reported earlier^{29,30}.

The present study indicated highly significant ($P < 0.0001$) impact of humic acid treatment on the cadmium availability in the investigated alkaline soil as well as on Cd-accumulation in plants. It might be attributed to interaction of humic acid with Cd²⁺ ions to form metal-humic complexes, and their effects on metal mobility in soil and their availability to plants^{31,23}. The strength of metal-humic complexes is highly pH-dependent and most of the stimulatory effects of humic acids on metal availability have been observed in alkaline soils^{32,33}. Thus, humic acid treatment exerted a stimulatory effect on plant cadmium availability and was well suited for metal bioremediation for enhanced phytoremediation potential of *Calendula officinalis* L. through soil plant rhizospheric processes.

Effect of cadmium and chelation on photosynthetic pigments :

The data graphically presented in Figs. 2(a-c) indi-

cated that the individual effect of cadmium and chelates on photosynthetic pigments were observed highly significant ($P < 0.0001$). However, the interaction between Cd and chelates was observed non-significant ($P > 0.95$). Varying levels of cadmium addition significantly ($P < 0.0001$) decreased the photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of *Calendula officinalis* L. The application of Cd at 30 mg kg⁻¹ + 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDTA registered the minimum chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene contents in leaves to the extent of 2.54, 0.61 and 0.60 mg g⁻¹ FW, respectively. The combined application of Cd at 30 mg kg⁻¹ along with 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDSS caused almost similar effect on the chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene contents in leaves to the extent of 2.58, 0.63 and 0.62 mg g⁻¹ FW, respectively²⁰. *F*-values for chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene contents with respect to chelates application were observed highly significant ($P < 0.0001$) to the extent of 8.71, 7.21 and 7.3 respectively. The reduction in photosynthetic contents due to application of EDTA and EDSS in the Cd treated pots might be ascribed to altered chloroplast structure leading to imbalanced photosynthetic activity³⁴. Degradation of photosynthetic pigments are induced by oxidative stress generated by chelates (EDTA and EDSS) which affect chlorophyll organization by chelating Mg²⁺ ions leading to reduced availability of the central metal ion for chlorophyll biosynthesis possibly due to impairment in the supply of magnesium and iron to the leaves of plants³⁵. Alternatively, cadmium may substitute magnesium in chlo-

Fig. 2(a). Effect of different treatments on chlorophyll-a contents in leaves of *Calendula officinalis* L.

Fig. 2(b). Effect of different treatments on chlorophyll-b contents in leaves of *Calendula officinalis* L.

Fig. 2(c). Effect of different treatments on carotene contents in leaves of *Calendula officinalis* L.

rophyll molecules³⁶. It was also visible that the greening process of plants was slower under chelate application than that of control pots, but the plant were able to acclimate to the chelators³⁷.

The individual application of Cd at 30 mg kg⁻¹ caused significant ($P < 0.0001$) and detrimental effect on chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene contents in leaves and their contents were observed to the extent of 2.62, 0.66 and 0.64 mg g⁻¹ FW, respectively. Reduction in

photosynthetic pigments by excess cadmium has been previously reported^{38,39}.

The EDTA-combined treatment comprising of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd along with 2 g kg⁻¹ humic acid and 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDTA produced comparatively lower contents of chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene in the leaves of plants to the extent of 2.64, 0.68 and 0.65 mg g⁻¹ FW respectively as compared to the EDDS-combined treatment comprising of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd along with 2 g kg⁻¹ humic acid

and 5 mmol kg⁻¹ EDDS to the extent of 2.69, 0.71 and 0.67 mg g⁻¹ FW, respectively. The present study indicates that photosynthetic pigments play an important role in the physiology of plants especially for protection mechanism against Cd-contaminated condition.

The application of humic acid at 2 g kg⁻¹ produced maximum chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene content which were recorded 7.12%, 8.24% and 8% higher over the control, respectively. Similarly, application of humic acid in Cd-contaminated (≥ 15 mg kg⁻¹) soils enhanced the chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene content by 4.2–7.35%, 8.97–13.64% and 7.04–7.81%, respectively, over non-humic acid treated pots³⁹. It is evident that content of chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotene in Cd-contaminated pots on the non-amended pots strongly decreases as compared to the control pots. At the same time, the plants at the amended treatments showed lower decrease in the photosynthetic pigments⁴⁰.

Application of humic acid boosted the content of photosynthetic pigments in *Calendula officinalis* L. which led to enhanced plant photosynthetic activities to counter the hazardous effect of Cd-contaminated pots. Therefore, it could be suggested to grow *Calendula officinalis* L., a potential phytoaccumulator, along with tested dosage of humic acid (2 mg kg⁻¹) and EDDS (5 mmol kg⁻¹) in Cd-contaminated soils. However, the highly contaminated

plants/plant parts after phytoaccumulation must be disposed off safely for the phytoremediation purpose.

Remediation efficiency or remediation ratio (RR) :

The study showed that applied cadmium had no significant effect on *Calendula officinalis* L. plant survival under pot experiments. All plants bloomed and no severe effect by metal concentrations was observed. Although mobility of cadmium from soil solution to plant tissues was successively enhanced by the combined application of cadmium from 0 to 30 mg kg⁻¹ and chelates. Further, addition of EDTA, EDDS and humic acid boosted the remediation ratio (RR) of cadmium in plants (Fig. 3).

Treatments without chelate application showed lower RRs values (<0.3) due to less Cd availability in the rhizosphere of the plants. The application of Cd at 15 mg/kg along with humic acid and EDDS registered the maximum remediation ratio up to 0.69%, however, the application of 30 mg kg⁻¹ Cd registered comparatively lower remediation ratio (up to 0.47%) than the with humic acid and EDTA treated pots. However, treatments having applied Cd along with either EDTA or EDDS or HA or composite of humic acid + EDTA or humic acid + EDDS possess higher remediation efficiency (≥ 0.3). The present study clearly indicates that the efficiency of phytoremediation remains better in the moderate Cd-contaminated soils (Fig. 3) as compared to that of highly Cd-

Fig. 3. Effect of different treatments on remediation ratio in *Calendula officinalis* L.

contaminated soils at 30 mg kg⁻¹. Mani *et al.* 20,25 observed almost similar results. The higher remediation ratios (> 0.6) in T₁₂ treatments (containing either humic acid + EDDS), out of total 18 treatments, proved the potential of plants as well as chelates (humic acid + EDDS) for enhanced clean-up of soils contaminated with cadmium in the slightly alkaline soils.

The study revealed that a cadmium-contaminated soil clean-up might be achieved through growing *Calendula officinalis* L. and its remediation potential could be enhanced through the composite application of humic acid and EDDS in the rhizosphere of plants. Meanwhile, environmental clean-up for other heavy metals from other ecosystems will be the future research criteria, which are being investigated by the authors. The strategy for enhanced clean-up of Cd-contaminated soils must be implemented in and around Cd-contaminated soils, especially along the sewage irrigated, waste water irrigated and Cd mining areas. Additionally, these areas can be developed as eco-tourism through growing ornamental plants to preserve the aesthetic beauty of wasteland as one of the important four component of the environment.

Material and methods :

Plant material and experimental layout :

The Sheila Dhar Institute experimental site, covers an area of 1 hectare, is located at Allahabad in northern India at 25°57'N latitude, 81°50'E longitude and at 120 ± 1.4 m altitude. A sandy clay loam soil, derived from Indo-Gangetic alluvial soils, situated on the confluence of rivers Ganga and Yamuna alluvial deposit, was sampled for the study. The texture was sand (> 0.2 mm) 55.54%, silt (0.002–0.2 mm) 20.32% and clay (< 0.002 mm) 24.25%. The properties of the soil were : pH 7.8, EC 0.28 dSm⁻¹, organic C (K₂Cr₂O₇ oxidation) 0.56%, total N 0.07%, total P 0.036%, CEC 19.4 C mol (P⁺) per kg, Total Cd 1.5 mg/kg, DTPA-Cd 0.56 mg/kg^{41,42}. The soil was ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve. Plastic pots of a 2 liter capacity (each containing 2 kg of air dried soil) were used. Identically-sized (5 cm height) *Calendula officinalis* plants were used. A single plant was transplanted into each pot. Plants were watered along with three levels of Cd concentrations (0, 15 and 30 mg kg⁻¹). Control plants were established under the same natural light condition receiving only representative soils.

The experiment was carried out in a natural light condition having daily temperature 28 °C and photoperiod 12.5 h. The experiment was replicated thrice and conducted in completely randomized block design following eighteen treatments. Total 54 plastic pots (having 18 treatments replicated thrice) were installed. The treatment combinations have been mentioned under the Table 1.

All the chemicals used in the study were of AR grade. Cadmium (Cd) was applied as cadmium chloride (CdCl₂), EDTA as di-sodium-EDTA (99%) salts, EDDS as tri-sodium[S,S]-EDDS salt solution (concentration 35% in H₂O) and humic acid as super potassium humate granule form. The seedlings were treated with three levels of Cd and one level of EDTA, EDDS and humic acid after 24 h of the treatment. They were transplanted under eighteen treatments. Soil moisture was maintained by irrigating the crops at interval of 5–6 days. *Calendula officinalis* L. var. Orange King was grown as a test crop and harvested at 60 days after transplanting for the aforesaid analysis. The plant samples were oven-dried at 60 °C for biochemical analysis and at 70–80 °C for the analysis of Cd.

Soil sampling and extraction of cadmium from soil :

In each sampling unit, soil samples were drawn from several spots in a zigzag pattern, leaving about 2 m area along the field margins. Silt and clay were separated by Pipette method and fine sand by decantation. For total Cd content, one gram of soil was mixed in 5 ml of HNO₃ (16 M, 71%) and 5 ml of HClO₄ (11 M, 71%). The composite was heated up to dryness. The volume was made up to 50 ml with hot distilled water. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of cadmium using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (AAAnalyst600, Perkin-Elmer Inc., MA, USA). For available Cd, 5 g of soil was mixed with 20 ml DTPA solution {di-ethyl-tri-amine-penta-acetic acid (DTPA) solution [1.97 g (0.05 M) DTPA powder, 13.3 ml (0.1 M) tri-ethanol amine and 1.47 g (0.01 M) CaCl₂ were dissolved in distilled water⁴¹ and was made up to 1 liter after adjusting the pH to 7.3]} was added and the contents were shaken for 2 h and then filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of Cd by the aforesaid spectrophotometer.

Soil physico-chemical analysis :

Soil pH was measured with 1 : 2.5 soil water ratio

using Elico digital pH meter (Model LI 127, Elico Ltd., Hyderabad, India). Double distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions. Organic carbon was determined by chromic acid digestion method, cation exchange capacity (CEC) by neutral 1 N ammonium acetate solution, total nitrogen by digestion mixture (containing sulphuric acid, selenium dioxide and salicylic acid) using micro-Kjeldahl method, Glass Agencies, Ambala, India and total phosphorus by hot plate digestion with HNO₃ (16 M, 71%) and extraction by standard ammonium molybdate solution⁴².

Plant analysis :

Plants were harvested after 60 days having higher phytochemicals at their maturity stage as suggested by Mani *et al.*¹⁸. Samples were carefully rinsed with tap water followed by 0.2% detergent solution, 0.1 N HCl, de-ionized water, and double distilled water.

Later samples were dried in a hot-air oven at a temperature of 45 °C, and ground to a fine powder. Plant dry biomass weight was recorded. One gram of ground plant material was digested with 15 ml of tri-acid mixture containing conc. HNO₃ (16 M, 71%), H₂SO₄ (18 M, 96%) and HClO₄ (11 M, 71%) in 5 : 1 : 2, heated on hot plate at low heat (60 °C) for 30 min and total cadmium were determined by the aforesaid spectrophotometer.

Determination of photosynthetic pigments by HPLC :

The upper second fully expanded leaves were sampled for analysis of photosynthetic pigments, at 60th day. The photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b and carotenoid) were extracted using the method of Barba *et al.*⁴³ with minor modifications. In brief, 2 g sample was ground in 10 ml of 100% methanol, centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 min to separate the supernatant, and these operations were repeated until the sample became colourless. The extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and then through 0.45 µm membrane filter. About 20 µL sample was injected for HPLC analysis. Analysis was performed using reversed phase chromatography (RP-HPLC) using DIONEX Ultimate 3000 series, comprising a solvent rack (SRD-3200), a pump (HPG-3200SD), a column oven (TCC-3000SD), and a diode array detector (variable wavelength detectors VWD-3100 and VWD-3400). The mobile phase consisted of

methanol and acetonitrile in 9 : 1 ratio at a flow rate of 1.0 ml per min. The column temperature was kept 22 °C. The wavelengths used to indicate the pigments were 430 nm for chlorophyll-a, and 450 nm for chlorophyll-b and carotene.

Remediation ratio (RR) :

The remediation ratio (RR) is defined as the ratio of an element accumulation in shoot to that in soil, which is calculated as follows :

$$RR(\%) = \frac{M_{\text{shoot}} \times W_{\text{shoot}}}{M_{\text{soil}} \times W_{\text{soil}}} \times 100$$

where M_{shoot} is the metal concentration in shoots of the plants (mg/kg), W_{shoot} is the plant dry above ground biomass (g), M_{soil} is the metal content in soil (mg/kg) and W_{soil} is the weight of soil in the pot (g). The RR values reflect the amount of a metal remediation by a plant from soil²⁵.

Data were analyzed by factorial analysis of variation (ANOVA) using various treatments as independent factors with the help of the sum of square (SS) and degree of freedom (DF). Graph Pad Prism (version 5.04) and MS-Excel 2010 software were used for drawing figures.

Conclusion

The applied humic acid promoted the dry biomass of *Calendula officinalis* L. but applied Cd at $\geq 15 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ suppressed the dry biomass and photosynthetic pigments of the plants. The concentration of Cd in the tissues followed the order : root > shoot > flower. The higher remediation ratio (>0.6) under both combinatorial treatments [either $15 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ Cd} + 2 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ humic acid} + 5 \text{ mmol kg}^{-1} \text{ EDTA}$ or $15 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ Cd} + 2 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ humic acid} + 5 \text{ mmol kg}^{-1} \text{ EDDS}$] indicated the possibility of enhanced phytoremediation of cadmium through *Calendula officinalis* L. under dual chelation. The phyto-availability of Cd increased moderately with 2 mg kg^{-1} humic acid and 5 mmol kg^{-1} EDDS applied was possibly due to supply of chelating agent that interferes with added Cd-fixation. The humic acid, which comes from domestic origin, has a strong affinity for cadmium ions. Phytoremediation through ornamental plants minimizes the risk of heavy metals toxicity in biological systems and remains as an innovative, cost-effective, environmental

friendly and sustainable technology especially for the restoration/management of the wastelands/contaminated soils, however, safe disposal of the contaminated plant tissues/parts must be ensured, for harnessing the maximum benefit of this technology. Thus, *Calendula officinalis* L. fulfills the necessary conditions for the phytoremediation of cadmium contaminated soil; and application of humic acid and EDDS further enhances its phytoremediation potential in the sandy clay loam alluvial soil.

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